

The Study of Children's Emotional Responses and Its Application to the Redesign of the Traditional Dental Handpiece

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Abstract: Statistics show that children often feel fear around dentists even though visits to the dentist are a necessary practice. The fear not only provokes great emotional anxiety, but also inhibits the dentists' ability to do their job. According to interviews conducted in this study, one of the main factors contributing to the anxiety is the design of dental equipment, especially the handpiece (dental drill). This paper presents the research and development process of redesigning a pediatric dental drill. The process examined not only the needs of pediatric dentists, but also the emotional effects the design had on children. Children's emotional responses were studied by administering two different surveys. Many interesting insights were discovered, particularly from the children's surveys, and incorporated into the redesign of a new pediatric dental drill. This study demonstrated a new approach to researching children's emotional response to medical equipment and redesigning such equipment to reduce emotional anxiety.

Key words: *children's survey, industrial design, emotional design, medical design.*

1. Introduction

A large percentage of adults are afraid of the dentist. The [1] *Australian Dental Journal* administered a telephone survey that acquired 7,312 completed surveys from Australian residents, aged 5 and above. According to the article, "The prevalence of high dental fear in the entire sample was 16.1 percent" (Armfield, Spencer and Stewart, 2006). [2] The *Journal of the American Dental Association* published an article called "The Prevalence of Dental Fear and Avoidance: a Recent Survey Study." This article summed up a survey, which used a random dialing procedure to shed light on patients' fear of the dental office. According to the article "results indicated that 11.7% of the respondents reported high dental fear, and another 17.5% reported moderate dental fear. Approximately 15.5% of the respondents surveyed have some degree of dental fear and are dental avoiders" (Gatchel, Ingersoll, Bowman, Robertson and Walker, 1983).

This anxiety has been the subject of several articles. The [3] *Journal of the Canadian Dental Association* published an article called "A Professional Psychologist and Dental Phobic Speaks..." In this article,

psychologist John Harvey writes about his experiences working with patients that have anxiety disorders. Dr. Harvey explains that these fears often start during childhood and worsen with age. “An unpleasant day in a child’s life can grow into an affliction that can cripple an adult.” Many adult fears of the dental office begin as a bad childhood experience there. A survey of dentists that was administered as research for this thesis reveals that four out of nine dentists cite previous bad experiences at the dental office as the root of patients’ fears.

1.1 Problem Statement

The fear of the dental office often starts with the dental handpiece. The dentists that were interviewed for this thesis point out this problem. According to a survey of 329 elementary school students, which was administered as research for this paper, 48 percent of children do not feel comfortable going to the dentist. When the dental drill appears, the number of children feeling uncomfortable jumps to 67 percent, and the number of children feeling very uncomfortable quadruples. The dental handpiece may well be the single most feared component of the dental experience.

Reducing the anxiety associated with a visit to the dentist also improves the quality of the treatment. According to the survey of dentists administered for this thesis, five out of nine dentists say that patients who bring anxiety to the dentist office hinder treatment. These patients often suffer unnecessary additional anxiety. Many of these fears begin during childhood, as described by Dr. Harvey. Therefore, from a designer’s perspective, the best opportunity to reduce anxiety is to make dental visits more pleasant for pediatric patients and to make treatment easier for dentists through the improvement of dental equipment. The goal of the process is to develop new dental equipment that both satisfies the dentists’ needs and creates a more neutral, emotional experience for pediatric patients. This thesis focuses on the redesign of the dental drill to make it easier for dentists to use and less intimidating to pediatric patients.

1.2 Need for Study

When a patient has a cavity, dentists use a handpiece to remove the tooth decay (which is what a cavity consists of) and prepare the tooth for a filling. According to the [4] Center for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) “More than half of children aged 5-9 have had at least one cavity or filling” and “78 percent of 17-year-olds have experienced tooth decay” (2007). That means that 78 percent of children require the use of a dental drill to remove tooth decay before they reach the adult age of 18.

For those children with improper dental care, life is more challenging. According to the [5] CDC, “the daily reality for children with untreated oral disease is often persistent pain, inability to eat comfortably or chew well, embarrassment at discolored and damaged teeth, and distraction from play and learning”. Tooth decay may even progress to the point that adult teeth need to be removed. The CDC also says, “By age 17, more than 7 percent of children have lost at least one permanent tooth to decay” (Center for Disease Control and Prevention, 2004). These children’s teeth could have been saved had the decay been treated sooner.

If the handpiece did not have such a menacing presence, fears of the dental office would diminish. If children's fears can be reduced, then many future adult apprehensions will consequentially be reduced. The result would likely be more adults visiting the dental office and receiving proper dental care.

2. Surveying Patients

After working closely with dentist to design a new handpiece that satisfies their needs and is also ergonomically improved, it is time to see what the patients think about it and see what adjustments can be made in order to please them and reduce their anxieties. This step is a bit more challenging since the idea here is to work specifically with pediatric patients. Soliciting adult opinions takes some skill, but soliciting information from children is even more challenging for many reasons. [6] John Touliatos and Norma H. Compton, authors of *Approaches to Child Study*, describe some of the difficulties of surveying adults:

Among the limitations of questionnaires are the diversity of meaning that may be attributed to a question by various respondents, the amount of education that may be required of a person in order to understand the questions and procedures, the difficulty of securing valid personal or confidential information, and the uncertainty of whether an adequate number of responses will be received to represent the population. (1983)

The most prominent problem with gathering children's opinions is that children's reading, writing and comprehension skills are not as far developed as adults'. This makes communicating questions to them, as well as figuring out the best way for children to communicate their answers, more challenging. [7] Ross Vasta (1982), the author of *Strategies and Techniques of Child Study* uses math as an example to explain this problem:

As children develop they may employ strategies or processes that either were simply not available earlier or were used inappropriately. For example, most 3 and 4 year-olds cannot answer questions like '5 + 3 = ?', where as 7 and 8 year olds do so readily. The nature of developmental change here is that older children have acquired a set of rules for addition...that younger children simply do not have. (Vasta, 1982)

[8] Touliatos and Compton go as far as to say, "Obviously, self-administered questionnaires cannot be used with young children." Though this statement certainly holds some truth, this thesis sets forth to prove that it is not entirely true. It is certainly more difficult to collect useful data from self-administered questionnaires for children, but not impossible. With the use of graphics and the minimal use of text, helped along with reading questions out loud, children can be surveyed with such questionnaires, as is exemplified a bit further along in this thesis.

[9] Michael P. Riccards, author of *The Making of the American Citizenry: An Introduction to Political Socialization*, explains other difficulties in gathering children's opinions. He describes difficulties that were encountered when trying to gather children's opinions on politics. He wrote:

First, some children (especially teenagers) may not take the questionnaire seriously. Second, boys and girls often tend to regard the questionnaire as a “test” and they are more likely to choose the answer they feel is correct rather than the one that most closely coincides with their feelings. Third, the questionnaire by its very phraseology may be eliciting a specific response. (1973)

Though the task is challenging, it is important that children’s opinions are collected in order to design medical equipment that reduces apprehension. This study does not involve surveying children one by one, though if a designer does have the time and resources for that, it is suggested. For those that do not, this study strives to show that mass surveying can be effective.

The problems of surveying children can be worked around by using more graphical pictures and less text. A picture is worth a million words, and everyone knows how to read a picture, though a surveyor must be wary when using pictures. Pictures, much like words, can mean different things to different people. And as is the case with words on a survey, the only thing a survey writer can do about it is to make the pictures as simple, straightforward and clear as possible. Here is one of the surveys being used for this study, which exemplifies these principles.

<p>Have you ever gone to the dentist? Mark 1 answer.</p>		Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>		
<p>How does going to the dentist make you feel? Circle 1 answer.</p>					
<p>How does this dentist tool make you feel? Circle 1 answer.</p>					
<p>What did you like the most at the dental office? Circle 1 answer.</p>					
<p>What did you dislike the most at the dental office? Circle 1 answer.</p>					
<p>Circle the dentist tool you like best. 					
<p>Circle the dentist tool you like best. 					
<p>Circle the dentist tool you like best. 					
<p>Circle the dentist tool you like best. 					
<p>Circle the dentist tool you like best. 					

Figure.1 Survey administered to children from kindergarten to 3rd grade

Some text is still used because it is impossible to make a survey that is purely graphical, while clearly stating the important points that this study needs to get across. It is more effective to make graphical answers than questions. In order to make the text easier for younger children, who could not read to understand, text is supplemented with related pictures and teachers read the questions to the children. The supplemental pictures help the children to follow along and better understand what the teacher is reading to them.

It is also important to note that questions number four and five on the first questionnaire are circle the answers, while they are fill in the blank for the second survey (shown in Figure.2). Fill in the blank is a much more accurate way to acquire the information for this study, but it is important to understand that there is no way for some of the younger children to fill in the blank with meaningful answers. For this reason younger children are given a simpler answering format. Therefore, fill in the blank questions are given to the older children who have no problem answering them, and simplified questions with circle the best answer are given to the younger children. Circle-shaped pictures are used to give a more intuitive indication that the answers are to be circled.

<p>Have you ever gone to the dentist? Mark 1 answer.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>	
<p>How does going to the dentist make you feel? Circle 1 answer.</p>			
<p>How does this dentist tool make you feel? Circle 1 answer.</p>			
<p>What did you like the most at the dental office? Fill in the blank.</p>	<hr/>		
<p>What did you dislike the most at the dental office? Fill in the blank.</p>	<hr/>		
<p>Circle the dentist tool you like best.</p>			
<p>Circle the dentist tool you like best.</p>			
<p>Circle the dentist tool you like best.</p>			
<p>Circle the dentist tool you like best.</p>			
<p>Circle the dentist tool you like best.</p>			

Figure.2 Survey administered to children from 4th to 5th grade

After a great deal of time is spent developing and rewriting these surveys (much like any other design process), plenty of copies are made and taken to Shades Cahaba Elementary School in Homewood, Alabama. There, 329 students are surveyed.

Figure.3 Children taking administered survey

2.1 Statistical Findings

After the surveys are administered, collected, and tabulated, there are 329 responses in total. 107 of those responses are kindergartners to 3rd graders who took the survey without fill in the blank answers. 222 of the responses are 4th and 5th graders who took the survey with the fill in the blank answers. Out of those children, 97.6% have visited the dentist. The surveys also show that 48% of children are not comfortable at the dentist office. When the handpiece is introduced to the situation the percentage of children that feel comfortable drops by 33% and the number of children that feel uncomfortable quadruples.

Figure.4 Percentages of children who are uncomfortable at the dental office

Around the Dental Drill

Figure.5 Percentage of children who are uncomfortable around the dental drill

The last part of the survey, which addresses the new design shows that the children prefer the new design to existing drills by 88.6%. The survey also reveals that 61.9% of students are drawn in by the color, and 66% of students like the look of a lugged grip.

Figure.6 Percentage of children who prefer the newly designed handpiece

Figure.7 Percentage of children who prefer color

There is no clear indication that the children are drawn to the shape or texture of the new drill, though there is also no indication that they dislike these attributes either. This may be due to the use of small pictures that do not clearly communicate these differences.

2.2 The Final Concept

The final model and final concept incorporates a number of new features that solve problems that were cited by dentists during the initial interviews mentioned earlier. The knife like appearance is alleviated with a softer shape, form and texture.

Figure.8 Features of the redesigned dental handpiece

By introducing a silicone rubber grip the tool is able to incorporate color, which is a desired feature mentioned by dentists during the interviews. These colors are preferred because they are more appealing to pediatric patients. The survey of children administered for this study showed that 63% of children preferred dental tools with color. To top it all off, silicone is a very durable rubber that is rated to withstand the extreme high temperatures that dental drills withstand every time they are cleaned.

Figure.9 Examples of the new grip's color options

Color can be added to more than just the rubber grip though. If the drill's body is made of aluminum, which is not only a typical material for these tools, but also a highly recyclable material, then the metal can be anodized to create more color choices as shown in Figure.10.

Figure.10 Examples of anodized aluminum color options

With softer shapes, forms, textures and materials, mixed with attractive color option, this new handpiece is more attractive to pediatric patients by 83% according to the children's survey. With all of these features used together to create a softer more pleasant appearance, this dental handpiece is intended to reduce the anxiety and apprehensions of pediatric patients, thus giving them a more positive experience at the dental office and increasing their chances of returning as an adult to receive proper dental care.

3. Study Accomplishments & Conclusion

This research and development project outlines a guideline for designing new medical equipment that will be more ergonomic and more appealing for the doctors that use it, while also reducing the emotional distress of the young patients. This study streamlines the process into a set of steps, which are easy to understand and practice, especially the children's survey. The survey is what allows designers to tap into patients' emotions for information to aid in designing tools and products with users emotions in mind. This children's survey can be easily adapted for the redesign of any child related products.

4. Motivation for Future Work

In the interest of fully verifying the effectiveness of this new handpiece and design process, it would be useful to conduct further research. This further research should study the new dental tool's effects on reducing children's apprehension at the dental office. It would be important to see how effective this new tool and design process is in reducing pediatric patients' apprehension.

It would also be advantageous to broaden the children's survey, by surveying a larger number of children from different sources in order to broaden the demographics. With this further studying it would be important to study the consistency of answers across different sources to verify the effectiveness of the survey.

5. Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank Professors Bret Smith and Shea Tillman for their valuable contribution to this study.

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